

ANESTHESIA OF CATS AND DOGS.

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Annotation.

In this article, a series of information about anesthetic drugs, premedications and their application techniques, used to perform surgery on pets, cats and dogs, which are an integral part of human life today, is covered.

Key words.

director, actor, film, drama, screenplay, performance, stage, theater, audience.

In all countries of the world, the attitude of people to small animals is of special importance. Most households in Russia, Europe, and Central Asia choose purebred cats and dogs. They provide favorable conditions for these animals to live well in their homes. They provide various foods for animals. They pay special attention to their health. However, regardless of how much attention is given to cats and dogs, even these animals

different diseases occur for different reasons. In such cases, animal breeders turn to veterinarians. Veterinarians make diagnoses based on the pathology of diseases. If the diseases are not treated in time, most of them have to be treated by surgery.

Many surgical procedures in cats and dogs occur in veterinary practice. Basically, surgical operations are performed for the following purposes. For example: treatment of a certain disease, castration of male animals, treatment of diseases related to the uterus and testicles of female animals, or cosmetic treatment of dogs and other purposes.

Of course, anesthesia is important for procedures requiring surgical intervention. For this, we will need to perform premedication and anesthesia

procedures in animals. Premedication, general or local anesthesia is important for surgical intervention. Incorrect anesthesia can lead to the death of the animal.

General anesthesia for cats and dogs is used not only during surgery, but also during treatment of animals: teeth cleaning, endoscopy. In addition to general or local anesthesia, it helps to fix the animals, facilitates the work of the surgeon or veterinary therapist. Non-inhalational anesthetics used in veterinary medicine include barbiturates, ketamine,

ksilanit, xylazine, zolitel, propofol and a number of other drugs. The choice of the type of anesthesia for surgical intervention in animals depends on the age and general condition of the sick animal, the size of the surgical intervention, the technical capabilities of the clinic (availability of anesthesia equipment, drugs, etc.) and the experience of the doctor.

Anesthesia in cats is a very complicated process. These animals are not suitable for the usual methods used for dogs. Some drugs cause the opposite reaction (for example, morphine), reduce body temperature by 1.5-2°C (ketamine, xylazine). Below are the types of anesthesia used for cats and dogs. For example: premedication is carried out according to general principles. Atropine is administered to cats intramuscularly or subcutaneously at a dose of 0.05 to 0.1 mg per body weight. Aminazine

2.5 mg/kg is administered intramuscularly or subcutaneously, 0.15 mg/kg intravenously. The following drugs are used for monarcosis: sodium thiopental in a dose of 20-22 mg/kg and even up to 60 mg/kg (Marek Zakievich, 1994); hexenal - 1% solution at a dose of 25-40 mg/kg causes anesthesia within 30-40 minutes; When ketamine is injected intramuscularly in a dose of 20-25 mg/kg (A.D.R.Hilbury, 1989), it causes anesthesia after 5 minutes, which lasts 30-40 minutes. Marek Zakievich (1994) ketamine

Recommends a dose of 20-335 mg. Then the duration of anesthesia increases to 40-60 minutes. After coming out of anesthesia, the animal is in a state close to hallucination for 5-8 hours. Depending on the severity of the animal's condition, the operation we can use ketamine in a dose of 20 to 35 mg/kg, depending on the expected volume, as well as which company produced the drug. In dogs, xylazine is anesthetized for 40 minutes when administered intramuscularly at a dose of 4.5

The animal will fully recover within 2-3 hours. 1 ml of 2.5% aminazine and 0.5 ml of ketamine are administered intravenously for 10 kg of animal weight. Infiltration with 0.5% novocaine solution is performed. It should be remembered that all the above drugs

causes a decrease in body temperature by 1.5-2°C, so it is necessary to take all measures to prevent this unpleasant phenomenon (keeping the room temperature around 21-25°C, etc.). In addition, xylazine causes vomiting and

the veterinarian should ensure that complications do not occur at this time.

Painless surgical procedures performed on cats and dogs require general or local anesthesia to immobilize animals during animal handling (tooth cleaning, endoscopy). Today, there are many drugs used to anesthetize animals in the territory of our republic, and they are effective in veterinary practice.

is being used. Among these drugs, the most widely used are xylanit, aminazine, zolitel, and are widely used for performing simple and complex operations.

These drugs come to our country mainly in the form of solution for injection from abroad.

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